

Development and validation of a RP-HPLC method for the determination of dextromethorphan HBr, chlorpheniramine maleate and phenyl propanolamine HCl in pharmaceutical preparations

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Abstract : A simple, specific and accurate reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method was developed for the simultaneous determination of dextromethorphan HBr (DM), phenylpropanolamine HCl (PE) and chlorpheniramine maleate (CPM), in syrup as pharmaceutical formulations. The final chromatographic conditions employed a Luna 5u C-18 (2)100A [250 mm × 4.6 mm i.d] column. The mobile phase was 0.1% TEA in water + ACN (77 : 23%) v/v pH 3 to 3.05 with *o*-phosphoric acid at a flow-rate of 1.5 ml/min. UV detection was performed at 260 nm for all the compounds. The retention times of dextromethorphan HBr (DM), chlorpheniramine maleate (CM) and phenyl propanolamine HCl (PE) were found to be 6.404, 3.595 and 1.673 min respectively. The method was validated in terms of linearity, range, specificity, accuracy, and precision, limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ). The linearity were found to be 1–400 ppm, and LOD were found to be 0.8, 0.16. 1 ppm the % recoveries were found to be 100.38%, 104.23%, 101.57%, respectively. The proposed method was successfully applied to the estimation of dextromethorphan HBr, and chlorpheniramine maleate, phenylpropanolamine HCl in combined tablet dosage forms.

Keywords : Dextromethorphan HBr, chlorpheniramine maleate, phenyl propanolamine HCl, RP-HPLC.

Introduction

Dextromethorphan (DM) is a cough suppressant. Chemically ent-3-methoxy-9 α -methylnorphinan hydrobromide. Chlorpheniramine maleate (CPM) chemically, 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N,N*-dimethyl-3-pyridin-2-ylpropan-1-amine is an antihistamine drug that is widely used in pharmaceutical preparations for symptomatic relief of common cold and allergic diseases. Phenylephrine (PE) chemically, (1*R*)-1-(3-hydroxy-phenyl)-2-(methylamino)ethanol hydrochloride is used as a sympathomimetic¹⁻⁴. Numerous UV, HPLC and HPTLC based methods have been reported for estimation of these drugs alone as well as in combination with other drugs in pharmaceutical dosage forms⁵⁻⁹. But no method had yet been reported for simultaneous estimation of these two drugs using HPLC in bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage forms. Therefore, the present work was aimed to develop and validate a new RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of CM and PE in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The present RP-HPLC method was validated following the ICH guidelines.

Results and discussion

Method development :

Several mobile phase compositions were tried to resolve the peaks of DM, CM and PE. The optimum mobile phase containing 0.1% TEA in water + ACN (77 : 23%) v/v pH 3 to 3.05 with *o*-phosphoric acid 0.1% TEA in water + ACN (77 : 23%) v/v pH 3 to 3.05 with *o*-phosphoric acid at a flow-rate of 1.5 ml/min. UV detection was performed at 260 nm. A typical HPLC chromatogram obtained during simultaneous determination of CM and PE is given in Fig. 1.

Method validation :

Linearity and range : Nine different concentration of the mixture of drug were prepared for the linearity studies. The calibration curves obtained by plotting peak area against concentration showed linear relationship over a concentration range 0.8–320 μ g/ml (DM), 0.16–64 μ g/ml (CPM), 1–400 μ g/ml (PE). The linear regression equation for DM, CPM and PE were found to be $Y = 46465x - 38841$, $Y = 85132x - 79058$ and $Y = 37841x - 30402$,

Fig. 1. HPLC chromatogram obtained during simultaneous determination of DM, CM and PE.

respectively. The regression coefficient (r^2) were found to be 0.998, 0.999 and 0.999. This indicates high degree of linearity. The results are shown in Fig. 2.

The average % recoveries for DM, CM and PE in marketed formulation were found to be 97.70%, 98.07% and 97.69%. The results revealed that there was no interfer-

Fig. 2. Calibration curves of CM, CPM and PE.

Specificity : The specificity studies proved the absence of interference, since none of the peaks appears at the retention time of DM, CPM and PE. The interaction studies in standard solution was also carried out by comparing peak of each drug individually and in the drug mixture.

Precision : From the standard stock solution mixed standards containing DM, CPM, PE, were prepared. Standard solution ($n = 3$) were injected with injecting volume 20 μ L. The intra-day and inter-day precision were assessed by analyzing standard solution. The % RSD found to be 0.47%, 0.24% and 0.69%. The lower value of %RSD indicates that the method is precise.

Accuracy : Recovery studies were carried out by applying the standard addition method. Known amounts of standard DM, CM and PE (standard addition method) corresponding to 80%, 100% and 120% of the label claim were added to sample of tablet dosage form separately.

ence of excipients. The results of accuracy are shown in Table 1.

System suitability parameters :

For system suitability parameters, nine replicate injections of mixed standard solution were injected and parameters such as the resolution, capacity factor, tailing factor, theoretical plate, retention volume and asymmetry factor of the peaks were calculated. The results are shown in Table 1.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) : The limit of detection and limit of quantification were found to be 0.8, 0.16 and 1.0 μ g/ml for DM, CPM and PE respectively. The values indicate that the method is sensitive.

Analysis of marketed formulation :

Analysis of marketed tablets (Concept Lab) was carried out using optimized mobile phase and HPLC conditions. The % drug content of tablets obtained by the pro-

Table 1. Datas of system suitability, accuracy and precision

System suitability :				
Parameter	CM	CPM	PE	
Theoretical plate	2160.183	4911.364	2662.59	
Resolution	7.496	6.786	0.0000	
Capacity factor	2.856	1.162	0.0000	
Tailing factor	1.863	1.564	1.222	
Accuracy parameter :				
Drug	% assay (without addition)	Drug add (%)	Drug recovered (%)	% recovery
DM	101.86	10	103.85	96.16
		20	116.73	99.08
		30	124.85	97.83
CPM	104.44	10	104.64	99.35
		20	112.32	97.75
		30	120.88	97.11
PE	100.40	10	106.48	97.19
		20	118.21	98.90
		30	125.63	97.03
Precision parameter :				
Sr. no.	Area of DM	Area of CPM	Area of PP	
1.	280269	483028	179359	
2.	277448	481132	180740	
3.	279932	482808	178451	
4.	280499	483913	181523	
5.	281342	484338	182002	
6.	281413	484538	181302	
Mean	28080.5	483298.8	180562.8	
Std. deviation	1322.89	1160.32	1256.9	
RSD (%)	0.47	0.24	0.69	

posed method for DM, CPM and PE was found to be 97.70%, 98.07% and 97.69% respectively. This showed that the estimation of dosage forms was accurate within the acceptance level of 95% to 105%. The results are given in Table 1.

Experimental

Shimadzu double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer (model 1700), Shimadzu liquid chromatography system equipped with a LC-10AT-vp solvent delivery systems M-10AVP UV/Visible detector. pH meter (micropro Labmate), analytical balance (Mettler) and ultrasonicator (Duex), acetonitrile (CAN) HPLC grade, triethyl amine (TEA) AR grade and *ortho*-phosphoric acid AR grade were procured from Rankem Fine Chemicals, Mumbai. Water HPLC grade was obtained from a milli-QRO water pu-

rification system. Reference standards of dextromethorphan hydro bromide, phenylpropanolamine hydrochloride and chlorpheniramine maleate are procured from Concept Pharmaceutical Limited, Mumbai.

Preparation of standard solution :

Chlorpheniramine maleate (CPM) stock solution was prepared by dissolving 50 mg of CPM reference standard in mobile phase and made up the volume to 50 mL with the same. Weighed accurately 10 mg of dextromethorphan hydro bromide (DM HBr) reference standard and 12.5 mg of phenyl propanolamine hydrochloride (PP HCl) reference standard to 50 mL volumetric flask. Dissolved in about 30 mL of mobile phase 2 mL of CPM stock solution was added in this, made up to volume with mobile phase and filtered. In the standard solution concentration of these drugs as follows DM HBr 200 ppm, PP HCl 250 ppm and CPM 40 ppm.

Preparation of sample solution :

20 mL of sample was pipette out and transferred to a 250 mL separating funnel. The sample was extracted 4 times with each 25 mL of ether to remove menthol, citric acid mono hydrate and propylene glycol. The aqueous layer was collected. From the collected aqueous layer 5 mL was pipette out and transferred to a clean 50 mL volumetric flask and made up to the mark with mobile phase and filtered through 0.45 µm membrane filter.

Preparation of mobile phase and its optimization :

1 mL of TEA was taken in a 1000 mL volumetric flask and mixed thoroughly with sufficient amount of HPLC grade water. Then volume made with same solvent. The pH adjusted to 3.0 with diluted *ortho*-phosphoric acid. The mobile phase was prepared by mixing already prepared 0.1% TEA and acetonitrile in the ratio 77 : 23% v/v the solution was then filtered through 0.45 µm membrane filters and vacuum degassed.

The mobile phase was allowed to equilibrate until steady baseline was obtained. The standard solutions containing DM HBr, PE HCl and CPM were run and various combinations of solvents were tried, mobile phase containing 0.1% TEA in water + CAN (77 : 23%) v/v pH 3 to 3.05 with *o*-phosphoric acid was selected. Since it gave sharp peak with symmetry and significant reproducible retention time for each three compounds.

Conclusion

A novel RP-HPLC method has been developed for the simultaneous estimation of CM and PE in marketed formulations. The method gave good resolution for both the drugs with a short analysis time below 6 min. The developed method was validated. It was found to be novel, simple, precise, accurate, and sensitive. The good % recovery in tablet forms suggests that the excipients present in the dosage forms have no interference in the determination. The %RSD was also less than 2% showing high degree of precision of the proposed method. The proposed method can be used for routine analysis of DM, CPM and PE in combined dosage form. It can be also used in the quality control in bulk manufacturing.

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